

BOOK OF PROCEEDINGS

2nd International Symposium on Interdisciplinary Performing Arts and Education (ISIPAE)

Change, Sustainability and Excellence

EDITED BY
HASAN SAID TORTOP
and **İLKER İŞSEVER**

11-12th December 2021
Istanbul - TURKEY

ISIPAE 2021

**2nd International Symposium on
Interdisciplinary Performing Arts and
Education (ISIPAE)**

11-12th December 2021

Istanbul, Turkey

Proceedings Book

Dr. Hasan Said Tortop and Assoc. Prof. İlker İşsever
Editor

Hosted by:

Association for Young Scientists and Talent Education

Istanbul, Turkey

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**2nd International Symposium on Interdisciplinary Performing
Arts and Education (ISIPAE)**

Proceedings Book

**Edited by
Dr. Hasan Said Tortop and Assoc. Prof. İlker İşsever**

Editor's Preface

Dear Academics and Artists

We are proud and happy to hold the 2nd interdisciplinary Performing Arts and Education (ISIPAE) symposium. This symposium is hosted by Young Wise Publishing Ltd. It is organized by the Association for Gifted Young Scientists and Talent Education (AYSTE). We would like to thank all academics, speakers and participants who contributed to ISIPAE.

We indicate that the papers presented and selected in ISIPAE can publish interviews and columns in our academic journals Rast Musicology Journal (Scopus indexed) and Journal for the Interdisciplinary Art and Education (Index Copernicus, Proquest etc. indexed), as well as in the semi-popular and semi-academic Music Notes Magazine. .

Our efforts will continue to make the ISIPAE symposium a worldwide brand and to make your research more visible. We are planning to hold our next congress with the face-to-face option, there will also be online presentations. In addition, we plan to organize an award in the field of performance arts every year. You can follow all these developments on our symposium website.

Hope to see you at the next ISIPAE

Best Regards,
Editorial

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1st ISIPAE Symposium Program

December 11, 2021, Saturday

10.00-10.10 Registration

10.10-10.30 Opening Speech

About Young Wise Publishing and Journal for the Interdisciplinary Art and Education Trends

Assoc. Prof. Hasan Said TORTOP

Director of Young Wise Publishing Ltd., London, UK

About ISIPAE and Interdisciplinary Performing Arts Trends

Symposium Chair: Assoc.Prof. İlker İŞSEVER (Istanbul University State Conservatory, Turkey)

10.30-11:45 Keynote Speech

Voice and Performance Expression and New Psychophysical Trends

SJ Harrison

California Shakespeare Company, Berkeley, USA The Royal Academy of Dramatic Art, London. Department of Theatre and Dance, University California, USA

Moderator: Assoc. Prof. Tuğçem Kar

1st Day – 1st Session: Session Chair: Assist. Prof. Dr. Handan ERGİYDİREN DOĞAN

12.00-13.15 Proceedings

The Use of Therapeutic Storytelling as an Emotional Expression Tool for Children's Piano Instruction

Ece Demirayak - Tan Temel

Therapeutic Dance Video Project With Breast Cancered Women Via Social Media

Elçin BİÇER

13.30-14:30 Keynote Speech

Living Music During the Covid

Cristina Pastorello

Moderator Assoc. Prof. Evrim Şahinkaya Kaplancık

1st Day – 2nd Session: Session Chair: Assoc. Prof. Sernaz Demirel Temel

14.45-15.45 Proceedings

The Examination Of "Makruli", A Georgian Polyphonic Folk Song, Performed By Macahela Seniors Ensemble

Damla ŞAHİN | Sernaz DEMİREL TEMEL

The Effect of Jaw Joint Structural Differences And Problems on Violin and Viola Performance

Zeynepnaz YILDIZ | Tan TEMEL

Analysis of The Family of The Georgian Folk Instrument Panduri, Analysis of The Sources of Georgian Folk Songs Accompanied by Panduri and Çonguri and Georgian Folk Music with Instrument Accompaniment Used in Panduri Education

Yudum ŞAHİN | Sernaz DEMİREL TEMEL

Accelerated Effects of the Pandemic in the Digitalization of Dance and the Embodiement of Digital Body

Onur TOPAL SÜMER

16.00-17:00 Keynote Speech

Changing Dance: Dancing Change

Rebecca Lazier

Princeton University, US

Moderator Assoc.Prof.Dr.Tan TEMEL

16.00-17:00 Keynote Speech

Don't Take No For An Answer

Assoc. Prof. Mary Price Boday

Moderator Assoc.Prof.Dr. İlker İşsever

19.00 Closing

December 12, 2021 Sunday

09.30-10.00 Registration

2nd Day – 1st Session: Session Chair: Assoc.Prof. Seda Ayvazoğlu

10.00-11.15 Proceedings

Investigation of Anthropometric Characteristics of Turkish Ballet Artists in Terms of Ballet Art Performances

Yağmur Arınlı

The Value of Event(ness) of the Live Performances through Digital Media

Asst. Prof. Dr. Handan ERGİYDİREN DOĞAN

The Anatomical Analysis Of Basic Posture In Ballet Education

Gökben Feda DÜNDAR | Seda Ayvazoğlu

An interdisciplinary evaluation in terms of nutrition and today's nutrition practices in ballet artists

Yağmur Arınlı

11.30-12.10 2nd Day 1st Panel Session

Panelists:

Assoc. Prof. Seta Kürkçüoğlu, Prof.Dr. Ayhan Helvacı, Language and Speech Therapist Betül Erataç Kağıtçıbaşı, Prof. Dr. Hakan Coşkun

Moderators: Assoc. Prof. Seta Kürkçüoğlu and Assoc. Prof. Tuğçem Kar

12.45-13:45 Keynote Speech

Serbian Choral Music

Prof.Dr. Zoran Stanisavljevic

Moderator: Assist. Prof. Mehmet Şahin Akıncı

14.30-15:30 Keynote Speech

When Should We Start Pointe Work?

Assoc. Prof. Emine Tuzcular

Moderator: Assoc.Prof. İlker İşsever

15.45-16:45 Keynote Speech

The Seek for Reform in Ballet at the Turn of the Century and XXI. Reflections on 21st Century Contemporary Dance

Murat Çatbaş

Moderator: Assoc.Prof. İlker İşsever

17.30 Closing Ceremony

Moderator: Assoc.Prof. İlker İŞSEVER (Istanbul University State
Conservatory, Turkey)

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Paper ID: ISIPAE1

Type: Oral, Speech

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: General

About Young Wise Publishing and Journal for the Interdisciplinary Art and Education Trends

Dr. Hasan Said Tortop

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Abstract

Young Wise Publishing Ltd. It is a company operating in the field of academic publishing for 5 years in Turkey and 1 year in England. It continues its 7 academic journals, more than 20 books, 3 academic congresses and academic consultancy services. With the support of the Journal for the Interdisciplinary Art and Education (JIAE) academic journal, he held the 1st Interdisciplinary Performing Art and Education Symposium on 24-25 April 2021. Your support continued in the organization of the 2nd ISIPAE, which is the continuation of this symposium. Young Wise Publishing Ltd. to continue performing arts and education research in an interdisciplinary perspective. It will continue to support researchers working in this field to come together and make their research visible all over the world. In addition to JIAE, Rast Musicology Journal (RMJ) also plays a supporting role in ISIPAE symposiums in publishing academic research suitable for its scope. In terms of the recognition and visibility of ISIPAE and other academic journals, planning is being made for this important event to be held face-to-face. We invite institutions and organizations such as universities, associations, foundations, companies that want to take part in the organization of ISIPAE to cooperate for the development of this organization.

Keywords:

Academic publishing, congress, symposium, JIAE, RMJ

Paper ID: ISIPAE2

Type: Oral, Speech

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: General

About ISIPAE and Interdisciplinary Performing Arts Trends

Assoc.Prof. İlker İŞSEVER

Istanbul University State Conservatory, Turkey

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Speech

Good morning everyone. I would like to welcome you all here today. I am Associate Professor Ilker Issever, a member of Istanbul University State Conservatory Performing Arts Department and the president of ISIPAE (The Fellowship of the Opera/Voice Education/Ballet and Contemporary Dance. I am very pleased to be here for the opening season.

Before moving on to the symposium presentations, I would like to tell you a little about this formation and our coming together. ISIPAE was formed about a year ago, with the gathering of our valuable academic colleagues from Turkey's most valuable universities, who supported and strengthened this unity and contributed greatly to its success until today. This formation brought together academics who had never known each other before, enabled us to work together, and I hope it will also sign under many important face-to-face events after the pandemic. In this collaboration, my esteemed colleague Assoc. Hasan Said Tortop did not spare us his magazine, publishing house, website and infrastructure, as well as all the infrastructure and assistance for the Zoom Meeting we are currently broadcasting, and had a great share in our gathering here today.

Another reason for the emergence of this association was the scarcity of written academic studies in our field and the fact that successful performance studies remained in a certain environment only in multimedia and never reached international areas. As a result of the studies we have done throughout our university life, when we all met the criteria of associate professorship, we encountered the importance and necessity of academic publications. For this reason, we all argue that these studies should be taken seriously, starting from university students, just like in other fields of science, and students should be encouraged to make poster and paper presentations at congresses and symposiums. At this point, we, as the ISIPAE family, fully support these studies and open our doors to our students who want to make presentations in their field.

We held our first symposium last April with the strength that our cooperation gave us. More than 400 applications and invited speakers and participants from many parts of the world made 15 beautiful presentations in the fields of Opera/Voice Training/Ballet and Modern Dance. Then, these studies were published in our proceedings booklet and some of them were published in our international journal Journal of Interdisciplinary Art and Education.

There is a very exciting morning planned. Today's meeting about Art Education such as; Opera-Voice Education, Ballet and Contemporary Dance together. Including what I know with wonderful announcements and presentations by great teachers all around the World and thank you very much for your presentations, information and the precious time that you shared with us. Thank you for being here with us.

In the presentations to be made here today, the duration of our participants will be as

specified in the program. Of course, after each presentation, there will be a section where you can ask your questions. For this, during the presentations, please do not forget to write your questions in the chat section. After the relevant presentation, the Moderators will forward your questions to our invited speaker on your behalf.

Well, as the president of this Symposium, I would like to thank you very much for participating today in the 2nd. International Symposium of Interdisciplinary Performing Arts and Education. We would also like to express my gratitude to my colleague and my dear friend Associate Professor Hasan Said Tortop and all other participants and contributors. I wish you all very good and healthy days. Now, I give the floor to my dear colleague, moderator associate professor Tuğçem Kar. Now let's get down to business. Thank you.

Keywords:

ISIPAE, symposium, interdisciplinary performing arts

Paper ID: ISIPAE3

Type: Oral, Speech

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Voice training

Voice and Performance Expression and New Psychophysical Trends

SJ Harrison

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Abstract

The way in which trends are created and how the attention we place on an idea creates a trend. She shared that from her vantage point, the most exciting trend in the US today in science, the arts and even in city and state government is that people are opening their minds to holistic thinking. Defining holistic in terms of this discussion: Holistic is the understanding that all the parts of a thing or system work together and are connected, thus separation is an illusion. How does this apply to the arts? As an expressive performer, singer or speaker we must use all parts of ourselves. SJ posed that with the industrial revolution, many cultures moved away from understanding the human being as a holistic system, and began instead to view the person as a machine. She explored this topic by giving a “case study” example of this limited approach (and its converse) from the perspective of healing physical injury, and the way in which one injury can impact and be informed by, all parts of the self. American Cultural Context: SJ Harrison also discussed the American cultural context for holistic practice, including the limitations of the American Method for actors, followed by an antidote to these challenges – The Holistic Performer: methods for using holistic practice in performance.

Keywords:

Vocal training, psychophysical trends, kinesthetic body consciousness

Paper ID: ISIPAE4

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Ballet

The Use of Therapeutic Storytelling as an Emotional Expression Tool for Children's Piano Instruction

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Abstract

This is an observational study backed by the theoretical background on the usability of therapeutic storytelling as a tool to support the expression of emotion in children's piano instruction. In the literature, there are only few studies on the use of therapeutic storytelling in piano instruction. Therapeutic storytelling is known to enable children to become aware of their emotions and process their feelings. This method is believed to support an instrument training approach in piano lessons for expressing internal processes through music, strengthen the bond between children and teacher, contribute to motivation. This research explores how the emotional structure of piano students aged 5-12 can be exposed through therapeutic stories and how these structures can be expressed through the piano. This paper presents examples of observation and practice from the researcher's lessons with piano students. The influence of therapeutic stories in helping children make sense of and express their emotions, and the theoretical foundations for connecting this effect with music have been discussed. Besides, the information on the future empirical study has been provided and the expected outcomes on the students as a result of this study have been mentioned. The study found that therapeutic storytelling could be used to compose music in piano lessons. It has been established that these stories could be used as materials that allow students to express their own internal processes in piano instruction. It has been that therapeutic stories can strengthen the bond between children and teachers, improving the quality of music education and positively affecting the motivation and creativity of students.

Keywords:

Therapeutic storytelling, music education, piano, emotional expression, composing

Paper ID: ISIPAE5

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Dance

Therapeutic Dance Video Project With Breast Cancered Women Via Social Media

Elçin BİÇER

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Abstract

During Covid-19 pandemics cancered people are suffered from the lack of social support and of home care due to quarantine and also faced with the treatment delays due to high viral risk at the hospital settings. With the mortal threat both in their bodies and also in outer world, this group have been affected from the pandemics the most. Also, losses and staying "disconnectedness" would lead loneliness, helplessness, depression, anxiety and correspondingly mental and bodily deteriorations. Therapeutic dance video is designed with the aim of creating a sense of "connectedness to each other", stiffening "desire to live" and "inner power" and the sense of "connected to the life" by providing their expressions to be seen and heard digitally in a dance/music form. The group was composed of 10 breast cancered women between the age of 18-60 from different cities if Turkey, 1 breast nurse and 1 therapist. The theme was "I love myself". The video was shared in October, "Breast Cancer Awareness Month". The choreography just contained head, arms and upper body because of social media frame. All participants performed alone the choreography at their home and recorded via mobile phones. In the collaboration with Metamazon Association, the edited version of the videoclip has reached 3000 people organically. Moreover, this project was presented as a case study during pandemics in dance movement therapy trainings in USA and in Australia by Dr. Marica Leventhal, the head of American Dance Therapy Association. Firstly, in individual online interviews, the benefits of this projects was examined specifically. Secondly, two online group meeting was set up for sharing the choreography. The emotional effects of the movements and the song personally, how they needed to individualized the movements, during which part of the dance they feel their own the most also examined. So the choreography has been recreated all together. The positive impact of the projects on the participants has gained with their verbal expressions. The reactions of the audiences also has shown that it has a positive impact on the audiences in terms of reviving inner power.

Keywords:

Breast, cancer, dance, psychology, pandemic

Paper ID: ISIPAE6

Type: Oral, Speech

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Opera

Living Music During the Covid

Cristina Pastorello

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Abstract

In this speech, singing education in Italy being the cradle of opera and voice culture is discussed in the context of the past, the present and the future. In addition, the extent to which the opera culture is internalized and the performance of opera based on this is discussed, taking into account the changing profile of Italian and international students over the decades. It will share our observations and experiences on the change, transformation and the adaptation in singing education, which was done one to one but turned into on-line during the covid pandemic.

Keywords:

Voice education and its transformation, singing education in Italy, pandemic and singing education, the sustainability of singing education.

Paper ID: ISIPAE7

Type: Oral, Speech

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Vocal Music

The Examination Of "Makruli", A Georgian Polyphonic Folk Song, Performed By Macahela Seniors Ensemble

Damla ŞAHİN¹ and Assoc. Prof. Sernaz DEMİREL TEMEL²

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Abstract

The songs performed by Macahela Seniors Ensemble have been traditionally passed through generations over centuries by oral transmission. In this study, the polyphonic vocal understanding of the Macahela Seniors Ensemble, which was transferred to the next generations in a master-apprentice relationship, is observed through the song "Makruli" performed by the ensemble. In addition to the musical terms and concepts that exist in general music theory, various terms are traditionally used in Georgian folk music. Basic terms such as Modzakhili, Meore Khma, Bani functionally determine the function of the voice and its function in the musical structure of the Georgian language. The "Makruli" song performed by the Macahela Seniors Ensemble was explained with these terms, and in addition, a descriptive study was carried out on the language in terms of syllable measure, rhyme and subject integrity. As a result of the literature review, no written source conveying the vocal performance practice of the Macahela Seniors Ensemble has been found so far. Through this study, the existing performance practice of the Macahela Seniors Ensemble was investigated historically and technically, and in this sense, it was aimed to create a resource for future studies on the subject.

Keywords:

Georgian music, Georgian vocal music, Macahela Elderly Ensemble, Makruli, polyphonic

Paper ID: ISIPAE8

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Vocal Music

The Effect of Jaw Joint Structural Differences And Problems on Violin and Viola Performance

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Abstract

A member of the string instrument family, the chinrest, which allows the violin and viola to be held more comfortably, was designed by Louis Spohr, a violinist, composer, conductor and musicologist who lived in 1784-1859, it was invented in the 19th century. It has been observed that the invention of the chinrest had significant effects on the performance technique of violin and viola performers. The chinrest has reached our days by changing its shape and diversity in the historical process. With repetitive movements performed by violin and viola performers during their many years of work, Temporomandibular joint disorders occur due to excessive use of the jaw in an inappropriate position. This condition becomes chronic and affects the performance and health of people. It has also been found that most of those with temporomandibular disorders have a habit of squeezing teeth called bruxism. In this research, the effect of structural differences of the jaw joint on performance in violin and viola performers will be discussed. In order to minimize the problems in the jaw discs and articular bone caused by squeezing the jawbone by addressing the physiological problems of the performers during the performance, a chinrest design created with ergonomic materials was realized. In this context, methods of softening the chinrest material are presented based on all existing ergonomic sample model studies. It is thought that improving the chinrest design by softening it with a material that takes a personalized shape will enable the performer to perform in a healthier and more comfortable way.

Keywords:

Violin and viola, musician health, jaw joint, orthodontics, temporomandibular joint disorder

Paper ID: ISIPAE9

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Voice

Analysis of The Family of The Georgian Folk Instrument Panduri, Analysis of The Sources of Georgian Folk Songs Accompanied by Panduri and Çonguri and Georgian Folk Music with Instrument Accompaniment Used in Panduri Education

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Abstract

Panduri is a Georgian folk instrument that belongs to the traditional stringed instrument family. As a performance practice, panduri performance is conveyed to the next generations with the "meşk" method, in other words master-apprentice method. Although the panduri is culturally important for Georgian people, it is thought that it will be insufficient to convey the playing styles applied today and the innovative playing styles that cannot be predicted in the future, due to the fact that instrument education is transferred with the meşk method. Therefore, there is a need for methodologically well-structured educational tools in order to transfer the values of panduri, which is an important carrier of oral literature and music, to future generations. In this study, the types of the Georgian folk instrument panduri are discussed in terms of its structural and musical characteristics. By making a literature scan on the subject, written sources named "Georgian Folk Music with Instrument Accompaniment" (Musika Kartuli Xalxuri Sakravecistvis) and "Georgian Folk Songs Accompanied by Panduri and Çonguri" (Kartuli Xalxuri Simğerebis Panduris da Çonguris Tanxlebit) were analyzed analytically. The examined written sources are used by non-formal education institutions. These resources, which are used as educational materials, in terms of playing styles; left hand signs, string numbers, position signs, signs related to right hand playing styles were evaluated methodologically. Thanks to this study, it is aimed to contribute to the literature by examining the notation of the types, playing styles and playing techniques of the panduri family, and revealing the theoretical studies needed by the panduri, which is an important part of Georgian folk music.

Keywords:

Georgian folk instruments, panduri family, panduri playing techniques, panduri education, methodology

Paper ID: ISIPAE10

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Dance

Accelerated Effects of the Pandemic in the Digitalization of Dance and the Embodiment of Digital Body

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Abstract

The art of dance strives to rapidly adapt its interdisciplinary theories and practices to the developments of contemporary digital technologies. While we examine the process of looking at the art of dance making through the lens of the camera in the 20th century, we experience the transformation of dance films in technique and practice, and their adaptation to the digital age with what the 21st century offers. In this study, ongoing dance films, video dance or early dance and digital technology culture examples by the pioneer artists in the field such as Maya Deren, Shirley Clarke, Charles Atlas, Merce Cunningham, Bill T. Jones, today's digital and mixed technologies, mixed reality, virtual reality, augmented reality and the evolution of adaptation to the new order and social media are examined. The montage/editing procedure in the production process of dance films can also be interpreted or observed as the re-evolution of choreographic analysis and choreographic creation in different forms. Especially under the influence of digital technologies, which accelerated with the pandemic period and became easier to access by "normalizing", dance as a performance form has been becoming into a daily expression and communication form on various social media platforms. For this reason, a brief introduction will be made to the trigger analysis of expressiveness that can be accessed and consumed quickly. While the pre-pandemic dance film festivals used to exhibit an example of an interactive community; the digitalization and transformation of festivals into individual experiences with the pandemic is a crucial issue that needs to be addressed and discussed. In this case, answers are sought to questions such as "with the current pandemic, whether physical stage and physical creation sets are imprisoned in digital environments and minimal spaces, or whether it accelerates and triggers vision-expanding possibilities by opening the doors to more accessible new telematic possibilities in the near future".

Keywords:

Dance, performing arts, digital technology, videodance, virtual and mixed reality

Paper ID: ISIPAE11

Type: Oral, Speech

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Dance

Changing Dance: Dancing Change

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Abstract

How can dance pedagogy evolve to prepare students for new choreographic practices, adapt to the changing interests of student populations, and respond to the global pandemic? Lazier discusses two recent courses taught at Princeton, Building Physical Literacies: Approaches to Contemporary Dance and Site-Responsive Dance and Choreography, that propose methods to highlight collaboration and community. Building Physical Literacies compares practices and performance methods of diverse approaches to the body and community in contemporary dance. Through a comparative embodied approach, students train intensively with rotating faculty to develop physical research built on a synthesis of experiences. Site-Responsive Dance, an online course, questions where dance can happen, examining the history of site-based art, site-responsive performance, and site-specific dance to generate student-led choreographic projects within the communities they live in. Dance education provides essential training to create community and tools for self-care, expression, reflection, and imagination: critical tools in this time of upheaval and change.

Keywords:

Dance, site-responsive dance, site-responsive performance, student-led choreographic project

Paper ID: ISIPAE12

Type: Oral, Speech

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Dance

Don't Take No For An Answer

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Abstract

My philosophy of teaching developed beginning with my earliest experiences in dance. My dance studies started at the age of eighteen upon my entrance to the University of Oklahoma in 1963. I knew from the beginning that I wished to become a teacher. My first ballet teachers were Miguel Terekhov and Yvonne Chouteau, from The Ballet Russe de Monte Carlo, and they taught from their traditions of Russian and Cecchetti styles. My late start in dance and a goal of excellence, inspired by my teachers, required that I learn to analyze movement and imitate the execution of steps in various styles.

My love of the art form, and my goal to become the best teacher I could be, drove me to want a professional career. Mr. Terekhov became an unintended inspiration, by convincing me that I had started too late to aspire to a professional career.

During my studies, I went to a nine-week summer program at Jacob's Pillow and studied ballet with Margaret Craske and modern with Norman Walker. Mr. Walker was a huge turning point. Norman Walker taught the May O'Donnell technique, and her roots were Martha Graham. That summer I learned a great deal about gaining strength and clarity of movement. The Jacob's Pillow summer was the origin of my pursuit of modern dance, most particularly Graham technique. Upon finishing my degrees BFA and MFA in Dance, I moved to New York and immersed myself into the Martha Graham technique, and Limon for its contrast, as well.

In New York, I danced in several companies, that were Graham or Wigman based. When I danced in the Mary Anthony Dance Theatre, Mary hired me to teach in her school as well. As a teacher, she wanted me to learn the Pilates matt exercises – a class that she taught. She was a friend of Joe Pilates and had worked with him extensively. Back in 1971, Pilates was not a household name. Through the Pilates, I learned the torso – particularly the lower back – was the backbone of dance (ballet, modern, etc.), and the strength of the rest of the torso next in order of importance.

David Howard and Maria Vegh hired me at Harkness Ballet to teach and immerse myself in the Harkness method, which was the Kneeland methodology. In 1966 the Kneeland methodology was a new approach to Principles of Movement as applied to ballet pedagogy, and was embraced by Rebekah Harkness, who purchased the method for her school and company.

Jo Anna Kneeland developed these principles through the filming famous dancers performing classical variations, and in the editing of the films frame by frame. She made a marvelous discovery; as a quote from Jo Anna Kneeland, in Dance Magazine 1966, she states, "We found, in short, that the traditional ballet pedagogy under which we ourselves had been carefully trained, and which we had always taken as truth, was often diametrically opposed to the actual facts of performance." The Kneeland principles can be applied to the variety of ballet systems or methods – Cecchetti, French, Vaganova, British, or any other – and to Balanchine, Bournonville, Robbins, Tudor, or any other style –

without changing the classical base of training.

Because of the Graham, Pilates, and Kneeland principles, it didn't matter that I started dance so late. I became a better dancer, and I was able to dance in professional ballet companies in Switzerland as a result. The best part was I was able to break down steps, the action for the step, and create exercises for correcting weaknesses in certain areas.

The whole time I danced professionally, I taught too. In 1976, I retired from dancing and went into full time teaching – many of my dancers have gone on to have professional careers in ballet and modern dance. And a few of them started late.

The physical requirements for the ballet dancer are stringent, but too often, a dancer, of great potential, does not pursue their dreams of a dance career, because someone has pointed out their physical defects and convinced them that they could not overcome these problems and succeed. I have found, through my early experience and later success in training dancers to a professional level, that it is the kind and the intensity of training, as well as the belief in the individual, that allows dancers to achieve their goals in dance.

Keywords:

Philosophy of teaching, ballet, dance, martha graham, pilates, kneeland methodology

Paper ID: ISIPAE13

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Ballet

Investigation of Anthropometric Characteristics of Turkish Ballet Artists in Terms of Ballet Art Performances

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Abstract

Determining the somatotype according to the anthropometric characteristics and starting ballet training according to the body type suitability of the dancer candidates are important for future professional success. There are 3 different body shape classifications: endomorph (fat), mesomorph (muscular) and ectomorph (weak). In a study on Bolchoi Ballet dancers, it was determined that female dancers showed ectomorphic features and male dancers showed mesomorphic features, while in a study conducted with candidates who applied for the Çukurova University State Conservatory special talent exam, 45.2% of the students who were successful in the exam were meso-ectomorphs, while % of the students who were found unsuitable were meso-ectomorph. 45 of them had endo-mesomorph features, 55% of the unsuccessful candidates were endomorph and 45.2% of the students who were successful were found to have mesomorph body type. high (21), while in a study in England, ballerinas were found to have mesomorph features. Revealing the body shape is important in terms of talent identification in childhood and is a determining factor in future success. As a result, based on the determination that 40% of physical fitness for ballet is due to genetic factors and the rest can be supported by regular work and proper nutrition, the studies revealed when evaluating students and candidates in our profession, where physical characteristics are at the forefront, generally highlight the mesomorphic and ectomorphic structure. conceivable.

Keywords:

Ballet, anthropometry, somatotype

Paper ID: ISIPAE14

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Dance

The Value of Event(ness) of the Live Performances through Digital Media

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Abstract

The purpose of this article is to argue the value of "event" of the live performances through digital media. Even they are presented as "live-performances", it is always possible to questions how long do they live as an event and how much they meet the common criteria to be assumed as a "performance" at all. In recent years especially with the impulse of Covid 19 pandemic conditions, most of the theatrical practices from classical forms such as opera, symphonic concerts, ballet, circus to contemporary forms like physical theatre, site-specific dance, dance installations, dj concerts; meets the audience behind the digital screens and be "live" by the help of online internet accesses. These stage practices are turned into film practices without much concern about film making but with intention to make these happen on simultaneous encounter with the viewer's time. However, calling them as "digital performances" or "performance on digital media" is so problematic and confusing for the sake of "performance" manner. After, these live performances become digital copies of the actual one and stays forever as dead records. As result, the quality of "event" and criteria of "being performance" are faded as soon as the stage practice is shared online. In order to deal with the first issue of the quality of "event(ness)", the related propositions of Gilles Deleuze in Logic of Sense and Jacques Derrida in A Certain Impossible Possibility of Saying the Event and his interview with Bernard Steigler in Echographies of Television – Filmed Interviews are taken as basis to discussion of the article. Then for the second one, the quality of "performance(ness)"/ "performativity" the certain aspects of performance which are differentiate it from rest of any theatrical practices are described. The intention of this study is to make aware the viewers or observers about the lack of "performativity" and "event as unique and individual live experience" of digital media online and on time sessions. Under the light of this awareness, entitle these broadcast as "digital sharing" or "live video" of performing art pieces is may suggested rather than using the term "performance".

Keywords:

Dance, performance, digital media

Paper ID: ISIPAE15

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Ballet

The Anatomical Analysis of Basic Posture in Ballet Education

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Abstract

Ballet education, which starts at a young age, is a long and arduous process. Intense physical work is required starting from the early stages through the entirety of a professional dancing career. During this process, uniformed incorrect executions of dance moves and moving techniques may result in various injuries of students who are in developing ages, and also may cause their dance life to end prematurely. In order to develop and execute anatomically and technically correct, and aesthetically flawless exercise movements during class sessions, a basic stance is required. This stance or posture improves body awareness and control in students, and further ensures that the necessary foundations for ballet training and technique are laid correctly. The objective of this article is to explain how basic stance is a prerequisite throughout the entire course of ballet education. In basic stance the location of bones, directions of joints and functions of muscles drastically differ from a simple standing position. Also, parts of the body must harmoniously align with each other. Because of these body related factors, various anatomical data have been analyzed and many different sources on anatomical topics have been thoroughly researched and subsequently distilled into this article. While dancing, incorporating an ideal basic stance enables all organs in the body to function properly and minimizes injury risks on the skeletal and muscular systems. As a result, free expressions increase and movement performances are brought up to peak levels. And most importantly the fundamental skill for continuing a dancing career in a healthy fashion is achieved through the understanding of basic stance.

Keywords:

Anatomy, ballet, ballet education

Paper ID: ISIPAE16

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Ballet

Interdisciplinary Evaluation of Eating Disorders in Ballet Artists

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Abstract

Like gymnastics, figure skating, and various dance genres, ballet also shows similarities within branches based on aesthetic performance, despite the differences between them. Due to the requirements of the artist candidates, they are exposed to a very busy work schedule and various rigid attitudes. However, in order to maintain current visual aesthetic standards, ballet dancers experience medical problems such as unbalanced nutrition, menstrual delays or interruptions, osteoporosis, stress fractures . It has been determined as a result of studies that malnutrition and strict calorie restrictions from adolescence cause the development of nutritional disorders, and the American Psychiatric Association established 8 subgroups of eating disorders according to DSM-5 (Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders-5) in 2013. They were divided into groups. In studies, the ideal weight of ballerinas for height was below 12%, 15.0% had anorexia, 19.0% had bulimia nervosa, 29.3% starved themselves to control their weight, 9.6% tried to control themselves by vomiting, and 4.2% resorted to laxatives, approximately 83%. It was concluded that the majority of patients showed symptoms of eating disorder. As a result of research, the US Dance/US Ballet Executives Council established a healthy diet for ballet dancers in 2011. developed a guideline. Education and a conscious approach are very important in the prevention and treatment of eating disorders. Dancers and their candidates should be knowledgeable in the aesthetic, technical and physiological aspects of art to cope with disability and pressure, educators and families should be aware of risk factors, early signs and symptoms, and serious problems if diagnosis and treatment are not successful. the performance and health of professionals will be negatively affected by the process; should be conscious of getting help from experts when faced with a problem with its medical, psychological and social consequences.

Keywords:

Ballet, anorexia, bulimia

Paper ID: ISIPAE17

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Voice Training

Interdisciplinary Approach on Voice

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Abstract

In this presentation, we will be with academicians working together in the same clinic and approaching voice from 3 different disciplines. Uludag University, Department of Ear Noise and Throat, faculty member Prof. Dr. Hakan Coşkun will present common voice disorders. Uludag University Head of Performing Arts Department Prof. Dr. Ayhan Helvacı "How should a healthy and quality voice be?" while explaining his question with his presentation; Betül Erataç Kağıtçıbaşı, a specialist audiologist and voice therapist, will explain the requirements for voice hygiene and the processes of voice therapy in voice disorders. The moderators will not only forward the participants' questions to the panelists, but will also pose questions to the panelists based on their own expertise in order to reveal the differences between voice therapy and singing therapy.

Keywords

Professional voice, voice therapy, singing therapy, voice disorders, voice hygiene, voice health, quality voice.

Paper ID: ISIPAE18

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Ballet

When Should We Start Pointe Work?

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Abstract

Going on pointe for the first time is one of the most exciting and magical moments in a young dancer's life. However, the decision to start pointe work is a very important milestone with serious consequences and should be made only by a knowledgeable ballet teacher. Allowing a student to go on pointe before the bones of their feet have begun to ossify is dangerous and can have potential harmful affects on an aspiring dancer's future career. Technically speaking, to go on pointe, it is necessary to continue to rise from the demi and the 3/4 pointe. Descending is with the controlled reverse action of the same movements. For correct positioning of the foot and ankle, the leg, calf and intrinsic muscles of the foot must be sufficiently strong. Since the base of balance is very small when the full pointe is reached, weight transfer and balance between muscle groups becomes even more important. Ideally, the weight should be carried by the first three toes. Toes should not be curled or clenched, and should extend downwards. Many factors play part in assessing if the student is ready for pointe work. Most importantly, the student must have had sufficient serious systematic training to develop technique and strength to prepare her for pointe work. Going on pointe before the student is physically and technically ready does more harm than good and can permanently damage the ankles and feet. Pointe work should not be started before perfect posture is achieved, turn-out established, coordination between the whole body including the spine, hips, thighs, legs, feet is fully developed, and the demi-pointe position can be securely used. The attitude and commitment of the student are also important points in determining readiness for pointe work. The structure of the student's ankle and foot is crucial for deciding whether or not the student should go on pointe in the first place. Anatomically, weight bearing on full pointe should not be attempted before the epiphyses begin to close. Wearing pointe shoes before the growth of the foot slows down can damage the cartilage and cause deformations to occur. Attempting pointe work before the age of 10-11 poses unnecessary risks. For students with hypermobile feet, it is essential to strengthen the ankle and foot before going on pointe. Aesthetically very beautiful, this type of foot is very vulnerable to sprains and injuries. Choosing the right shoes is also of utmost importance for preventing injuries. Using correct technique, a professional dancer can use pointe shoes for many years without any injury. Sickling the foot outward can cause the inner ligaments of the foot to get overstretched, so more weight is put on the big toe and can result in hallux valgus deformities. Although aesthetically not pleasing, inward sickling is less harmful, but ankle sprains are more common if the external ligaments are overstretched. In conclusion, there is no ideal age to start pointe work, the student should only be allowed to wear pointe shoes when she is ready. This age should never be less than ten years old. Both students and parents should be educated about the risks of starting pointe work too early and informed about potential harmful effects.

Keywords

Ballet, Pointe, pointe work, injury, deformities

Paper ID: ISIPAE19

Type: Oral, Abstract

Article topics in the ISIPAEducation: Ballet

The Seek for Reform in Ballet at the Turn of the Century and XXI. Reflections on 21st Century Contemporary Dance

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Abstract

After the great development and success of Romantic Ballet in the middle of the 19th century in Paris, towards the end of the century, ballet turned into a secondary art form and began to be integrated into operas, taking place in music halls and variety shows. Ballet turns into performances in which male audience members watch female dancers as erotic objects and takes a completely different path. In the same period, under the leadership of the French choreographer Marius Petipa in Russia, St. Petersburg and Moscow are experiencing the triumph of classical ballet. While Paris has a great interest in Russian culture, music and art, Russia is dependent on France to modernize its industry and communication. The 20th century leads to a redefinition of the dancer and the dancing body view, separately as the male and female body. Ballets Russes with their talented and powerful dancers; It opens up the fame of future French male dancers, especially with male dancers with masculine bodies. Out of this masculinity, androgyny also arises in order to reflect the spirit of the period. Among these developments, the female dancers, on the other hand, break their roles as light-than-air and fly fairy-like, as in the Romantic period, and create a masculine day. and they become able to show their true femininity in dynamism. This break has evolved to the present day and sheds light on the formation of contemporary dance. Dance includes political elements with a great return to universality and continues to develop in different forms. Dance Theater looks at the Art of Dance from a completely different perspective by including the elements of the performing arts that are not found in the traditional concept of Ballet..

Keywords

Dance, ballet, 21st century

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